

Goal: To aid decision making on where to protect additional forest habitat in Sabah, Malaysian Borneo. Designed to form one input to a holistic planning exercise, we focus specifically on preserving connectivity between protected areas (PAs) under future climate warming scenarios.

Study area in Sabah: remaining forest areas (available for recommendation for protection - green) designated by 40 MT or more aboveground carbon threshold, with existing totally protected areas (yellow).

CONDATIS PARAMETERS

What kind of species are we interested in?	Multiple – long-distance & short-distance dispersers , specialised to existing temperatures
What is our source and target?	Sources are lowland PAs ; target is upland PAs
Why do our species need to move?	Climate change – to track habitat that has a suitable temperature
What constitutes habitat?	Native forest
What kind of prioritisation are we performing?	Identifying the most important <i>additional</i> habitat patches to formally protect to maximise long-term connectivity
Who will be interested in the results?	Sabah Forestry Department and other stakeholders

SUMMARY CONDATIS RESULTS

A: Speed loss map for one example PA, showing how much connectivity is lost if each unprotected forest cell is lost from the landscape (Axes show metres on UTM grid)

B: Map of **overall priority of habitat cells** outside existing Totally Protected Areas that are most important in enabling connectivity for species tracking climate change. Colour scale shows relative priority from appropriately weighted results of all source PAs.

Using the Condatis ‘prioritisation by dropping’ outputs from 143 lowland PAs, we developed a scoring method to identify the most important unprotected ‘climate change escape routes’ across Sabah. In brief we score a cell highly if it is:

- very important for one source (max)
- important for many sources (count)
- important for large sources (using area to power 0.25)

